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NERSC Technical Report 335

NETWORK BUILDING ON OCEANIC MESO-SCALE EDDIES AND MARINE ECOSYSTEMS

by

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REPORT

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Background and Objective:

This project involved preparation, participation and follow-up of convener responsibilities for a session at the American Geophysical Union Ocean Science Meeting 2014 <http://www.sgmeet.com/osm2014/default.asp>, as a means of developing our network within the field of oceanic meso-scale eddies and their influence and interaction with the marine ecosystem.

Meso-scale oceanic eddies are circular flow patterns present in large parts of the world oceans. In Norwegian waters the wide shelf area between the coastal current and the Atlantic inflow off the shelf is dominated by eddies, both transient eddies and stationary eddies locked to the bottom topography, for example the Lofoten basin eddy (Søiland and Rossby, 2013). The eddies influence the ocean and the accompanying biological habitat significantly, and effects on for example the transport of fish eggs and larvae (Sundby et al., 2013), phytoplankton blooms, nutrient transport, dispersion of pollutants and plankton (Samuelsen et al., 2012), as well as response in fish (Godø et al., 2012) have been documented. Some of the effect of meso-scale eddies in Norwegian waters is described by Samuelsen & Hjøllo in a popular science article in (feature story) in Bergens Tidende March 2012.

Advancing the study of meso-scale eddies and their interaction with the ecosystem requires application of new technology and a collaborative research approach and international cooperation is necessary.

For example:

- Eddies influence the ecosystem through mixing and is through to have some of the strongest vertical velocities found in the open ocean, these quantities are extremely hard to measure in the ocean.
- Satellites can image eddies at the ocean surface and in some instances give several variables (e.g. chlorophyll and temperature) simultaneously, but we need to be able to connect the surface dynamics to what goes on below the surface.
- Eddies can be dynamic and transient, but acoustic techniques and optical imaging techniques give unique opportunities to map eddies with respect to both fish and plankton.
- High-resolution realistic modelling give unique opportunity to study the eddy dynamics, but must always be backed up by data collected in the field.

Several of the themes above themes were addressed on one or more presentation.

Description of session:

Title: Physical-biological interactions in meso-scale eddies: governing processes and implications for the marine ecosystem

Description: Meso-scale eddies impact marine ecosystems at multiple trophic levels by influencing nutrient input, primary production, advective transport, and aggregation and dispersion of larvae and plankton. These properties of the eddies may also make them attractive for higher trophic level animals. New in-situ observation techniques combined with real-time information from satellites have stimulated more detailed studies of mesoscale eddies. This session addresses how meso-scale physical processes interact with biology at all trophic levels. Studies addressing trophic

interactions within eddies and how these are influenced by the physics are especially relevant. Studies focusing on nutrient input, plankton, larvae or fish production and distribution in relation to meso-scale eddies are also welcomed. Further, we encourage contribution on eddies as feeding habitats for marine animals and birds. We seek contributions on both detailed studies of individual eddies and integrated effects of meso-scale eddies in time and space. We welcome multiple-sensor field studies as well as modeling approaches, and in particular studies combining several approaches.

Scientific highlights

The scientific content of the session was quite broad encompassing global scales as well as local phenomena and spanning most tropic levels. On the global scale remote sensing is a favored tool, classifying eddies by use of sea-surface height and/or SST and evaluating their influence on primary production by the use of ocean color. These techniques can also be used to deduce the mechanism by which the eddies influence the chlorophyll distribution. The effect of resolving eddies were also demonstrated in a global model, since the eddies has a particularly large influence in the Southern Ocean; an area important for the global carbon cycle. Going to more local scales and further up the food chain, it was demonstrated that lobster larvae in the Leuwin current of Australia were healthier in cold core eddies than warm core eddies, while anticyclonic eddies in Alaskan waters were shown to be beneficial for salmon recruitment. It was demonstrated through a model that the eddies effectively isolated individuals from the surrounding waters, which may have a large effect on fish recruitment. Finally eddies seem to influence recruitments of farmed salmon in Alaskan waters, but the actual mechanism behind is still not clear as it is a remote effect. Bacteria was also addressed by showing that eddies can have a local and strong effect on the oxygen minimum zone found in many oceans. Some studies had used new observational techniques, for example the oxygen minimum study had followed an eddy with a multi-instrument float for a very long period. Off Japan an experiment using multiple autonomous floats have been launched in order to characterize the physical and biological properties of rings spun off the Kuroshio Current. The full session program with links to abstracts can be found at <http://www.sgmeet.com/osm2014/sessionschedule.asp?SessionID=015>

Outcome of project

The AGU OSM conference is a bi-annual event that this year gathered about 5600 oceanographers from all over the world for a 5-day conference. For the purpose of the session we contacted Carol Ladd at NOAA/PMEL Seattle, who co-convened the session. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration/ Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory (PMEL) in Seattle (USA) is a federal laboratory that makes critical observations and conducts groundbreaking research to advance knowledge of the global ocean and its interactions with the earth, atmosphere, ecosystems, and climate.

We received 26 contributions in total and out of these we were allocated time for 8 oral presentations. The oral presentations chosen were those addressing the session description most accurately, making sure that interactions between physics and biology were addressed. We also prioritized that the oral presentations as a whole addressed multiple spatial scales and trophic levels. Finally we made sure should that we had a good geographical distribution of the speakers affiliations and that we also had student presentations. The oral presentations was organized so that the theme

started on global studies with the focus on lower trophic levels going to more local studies with the focus on higher trophic levels. The oral session was held on Monday afternoon and immediately followed by the poster session, were the remaining 18 submission were presented. One of the posters (copy enclosed) presented recent work by Samuelsen, Hjøllo, Ladd and others, as a direct result of the cooperation established through the preparations of the session event.

The oral session was well attended with an almost full meeting room and the poster session was also very busy. The organizer of the conference had put an effort into highlighting the poster session by not scheduling arrangements confliction with the poster session, and also this event were well attended with informal atmosphere and possibilities for networking and information exchange. The session was concluded by inviting the session presenters for a joint dinner of which 15 of the presenters joined. The authors are grateful for the support from the Research Council which made it possible for us to participate in the organization of a large, international conference as well as increasing our network within the field of meso-scale eddies.

Future work

Impact of meso-scale eddies on the marine ecosystems attracts interest in the global scientific community, and we will continue to work on this subject by utilizing our existing network as well as new contacts established through this project. At the present moment a new centre for ecosystem dynamics, the Hjort Centre has been established and we wish to establish a working group on meso-scale eddies within this centre.

We will seek project funding for further meso-scale eddy research, and plan to follow up our contact within this field by arranging a local workshop on this theme within a years time. We have currently submitted an application for support for an exchange student summer internship within the POME exchange program with Dalhousie University in Canada. The aim of this project is analyze model-simulated data with respect to meso-scale eddies in the Norwegian Coastal Current.

Use of resources:

The project was completed as planned with a 30/70 distribution of travel cost and time preparation and participation.

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APPENDIX A:

Poster presented by session conveners at the poster session

OSM 2014
015 - Physical-biological interactions in mesoscale eddies: governing processes and implications for the marine ecosystem

Poster no. 312

A multi-method approach to linking mesoscale structures to distribution of biomass of higher trophic levels

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Multi-method approach for studying mesoscale eddies

Concept

- Eddies were detected using remote sensing of ocean color, SST, or synthetic-aperture radar (SAR). On the right, an example of surface roughness from an eddy that was detected and surveyed during November 2009.
- Acoustic data was collected on a transect crossing an eddy. These data can be collected while underway (4-5 hours) providing a synoptic picture of the distribution of biomass as well as the upper ocean current structure from ADCP. On the right, color represents the biomass density in an eddy. There are areas of high biomass at the eddy edges close to the surface and the mesopelagic layer is pushed down several 100 meters compared to the waters outside the eddy.
- The eddy was also surveyed using CTD, water sampling, and trawl. More time was required for these measurements, giving a less synoptic picture than the acoustics. On the right is the density of eddy core water (blue) and water outside the eddy (red). The eddy core consists of the Coastal Current (blue dashed line).
- Several model simulations of eddies were run. The simulations range from advection of passive particles to more complex coupled physical-biological models. The models are used to explain some of the patterns of biomass observed in the field. The images on the right show the modeled aggregation of passive particles along the edge of an anti-cyclonic eddy.

Example

Introduction

The area outside the Lofoten Islands in the Norwegian Sea (the Lofoten Basin) is an area rich in mesoscale eddies.

The eddies are shed from instabilities along the front between coastal and offshore waters or triggered by the sudden widening of the shelf at about 70° N.

The area was used as a test-bed for studying interactions between mesoscale eddies and the marine ecosystem using a combination of remote sensing, in-situ observations and numerical modeling (Godø et al., 2012; Samuelsen et al., 2012).

Based on further analysis of the acoustic measurements, it was hypothesized that eddy age may be responsible for the different patterns of biomass distribution observed in different eddies.

Here we use a coupled biological-physical modeling system to study the physical properties and resulting biological response in eddies of different ages.

Properties of eddies at different ages

Temperature of the eddies on day 120, the eddies appear to cool with age, but this probably varies with the season.

Salinity in the different eddies varies widely, all eddies start out with a core of relatively fresh coastal water.

Three-dimensional current structure for each of the eddies (left). Of the four eddies, the oldest have the strongest signal at depth. The temporal development of the minimum relative vorticity in each eddy with time is shown below.

The vertical velocity (m/day) in each eddy averaged over 11 days from day 115 to 125, moving with the eddy. The black contours are averaged relative vorticity plotted to help locate the eddy in the plot. Using the vorticity at the center of the eddy as an indicator, A1 and A4 are weakening over this period, while A2 and A3 are intensifying. Both A1 and A4 have an average upwelling velocities at the center and hence divergence of the surface currents.

Model description

- PHYSICAL MODEL:** A configuration of HYCOM for the Norwegian Sea with a resolution of 2.3 km was used. The simulation period was January to July of 2005.
- NPZD MODEL:** Primary production was simulated using an 11-component NPZD model for the Norwegian Sea. NORVECOM - this model provides the food for the IBM, but the two models are not coupled.
- IBM MODEL:** An individual based model (IBM) for the copepod *Calanus finmarchicus*, the dominant species of zooplankton in the Norwegian Sea, was used for simulating zooplankton biomass. The use of a life-cycle model for zooplankton allows us to study the impact of behavior on biomass distribution in an eddy field.

C. finmarchicus overwinter at depth and start ascending towards the surface between February and April.

- The female can produce eggs both using fat reserves from overwintering and after feeding on the spring bloom.
- The individuals go through 13 developmental stages before, depending on the condition, either reproduce or descend to depth to enter diapause.
- During their time at the surface, the copepodite stages perform diurnal migration, while the nauplius stages do not. The amplitude of the diurnal migration becomes larger as the stages progress.

The superindividual concept: The large number of individuals of zooplankton (several thousand per m³) necessitates the introduction of super individuals, where a super individual represents a dynamic number of individuals with the same attributes. This allows us to use fewer particles, but still represent the number of individuals, biomass etc.

Modeled distribution of plankton in eddies

In this region eddies are regularly shed off on the front between the less dense coastal current (blue) and the offshore, denser Atlantic water (green/yellow; Fig. 2). We identified 4 anticyclones of different ages that will be characterized below. A1 is at this stage 15 days old, A2 is 40 days, A3 is 60 days and A4 about 70 days old.

Modeled density (color) together with contours of relative vorticity, positive is black and negative is pink.

The spatial distribution in the number of individuals is reflected in the reproduction, the production of eggs is significantly higher in eddy A2 and A3 (Fig. 5). Neither difference in food availability (Fig. 4) or temperature (Fig. 6) can explain the difference in egg production between the eddies. The temperature decreases with age, A1 is the warmest and A4 the coolest (Fig. 6). The model requires the individuals to be within 50 meters of the surface to spawn, and the individuals in eddy A1 and A4 reside deeper in the water column and thus reach the surface layer later than the individuals in A2 and A3.

Food availability (mg C/m³) averaged over days 100-120.

Number of egg produced per female on day 120.

Conclusions

- Over the course of its lifetime an eddy can spin down, re-intensify or merge with others. Thus, it is not easy to classify the properties of the eddy by age alone and therefore age can probably not be used as explanation of different biomass distribution in different eddies.
- There is aggregation of particles at the center in eddy A2 and A3, the two oldest that are intensifying. There are also more eggs produced per female in these eddies, further increasing the number of individuals in these eddies.
- The core of eddies A1 and A4, the two eddies that are weakening, have few individuals and additionally a low egg production per female. Divergence of currents at the eddy center as well as proximity to the coastal current where there are few individuals explain the low number of individuals in the eddies. The low reproduction rate appears to come from individuals generally residing deeper in the water column and reaching the surface layer after exiting diapause.

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